

Determinants of Financial Reporting Quality in Agripreneurship Performance in Nigeria

BY

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ABSTRACT

This study focused on the determinants of financial reporting quality in private sector organisations with particular reference to Dangote group of companies in Nigeria. Ex-post facto research design was adopted in the study. Our data were extracted from annual reports of private - agripreneurship organizations operating in Nigeria from 2020 to 2024, and analyzed with the aid of correlation and regression analyses using Statistical version 14. From the regression results, the variable of internal control disclosure [Coef. = 12.165(0.005)] has a significant positive effect on timeliness of annual reports of the organisations during the period under study. This result is in line with apriori expectation but inconsistent with the null hypothesis. The variable of management financial expertise [Coef. = 12.722(0.002)] has a significant positive effect of timeliness of annual reports of the private - agripreneurship organisations during the period under study. This result conforms to apriori expectation but inconsistent with the null hypothesis, implying that an increase in the number of Directors with financial expertise will significantly increase timeliness of annual reports of the private sector - agripreneurship organisations. The variable adoption of IFRS [Coef. = 7.058 (0.604)] has a significant positive effect of timeliness of annual reports of the private sector - agripreneurship organisations during the period under study. This result conforms to apriori expectation and is consistent with the null hypothesis, hence implying that the adoption of IFRS significantly increased timeliness of annual reports of agripreneurship companies in Nigeria. Financial reporting quality is crucial in maintaining the efficiency of financial markets because market participants, such as investors, lenders, and regulators, rely on financial reporting information to make decisions. It was therefore recommended that Dangote group of agripreneurship companies should ensure periodical monitoring and evaluation of their internal control systems. The actual assessment can be executed by the organization's management in order to promote financial reporting quality among private sector organizations in Nigeria.

Keywords: Agripreneurship, Financial Reporting, Nigeria Exchange Group, Private Sector Organizations, Quality of Sservice.

1. Introduction

The preparation and presentation of financial statements of the private sector entities in Nigeria have hitherto been rooted in the traditional cash basis of accounting, characterized by low level of accountability, transparency as well as high exposure to fraud and corruption in the accounting reporting system (Bastani, *et al.*, 2012). However, the need to go from the traditional cash accounting system to the accrual-based system of accounting in the private sector entities has brought about an innovation in the areas of recognition of economic events, recording of all stocks of assets and liabilities in the statement of financial position, improved monitoring of current, long-term and contingent liabilities as well as consolidation of all entities under the management's control (Joe, *et al.*, 2016). Hence, in order to ensure and maintain people's trust in the organization, shareholders' funds ought to be managed in a transparent manner.

There are several studies that have been done on the determinants of quality of financial reports. Chan (2016), provided a lot of credence to the increasing importance of international accounting standards particularly to developing countries once they borrow or rely on foreign aid and would be a useful tool not only to account for these resources but also to compare the use of them between reporting periods. Kariuki, *et.al*, (2013), in their study titled, "Institutional investor's perception on quality of financial reporting in private sector for companies listed on NSE", stated that users of financial reports must understand the contexts in financial statements in order to use them effectively. They argued that entities must first recognize investors and other users of financial reports as customers. They emphasized that financial reports must be current, comprehensive, easy to understand and accurate. The study concluded that investors perceived the financial reports quality in terms of qualitative characteristics.

1.1.1. Scope of the study

This study focuses only on agricultural sector of the Nigerian economy with particular focus on the Dangote agribusiness companies registered on the Nigeria Exchange Group (formerly the Nigeria Stock Exchange), during the period under study; that is, a total of eleven years (2003-2014). The other reason for the choice of Dangote group of companies is predicated upon its being the largest single private enterprise operating in the field of agriculture in Nigeria, having more than every other employer's contribution in terms of human capital employment, thereby giving it wider

visibility. Dangote agricultural companies have branches in almost every state of Nigeria and in overseas.

1.1.2 Financial reporting quality

Financial reporting within the context of public sector is a process of collecting, classifying, summarizing, and reporting accounting information that relates to government activities so as to allow citizen participation and holding elected officials accountable which also provides the background for people to have informed judgement on government performance and accountability assessment (Bastani, *et al.*, 2012). It's been contended that financial reporting is not only a final output; the quality of the process depends on each of its parts, including disclosure of the corporate's transaction, information about selection and application of accounting policies and knowledge of the judgment made (Blanchet, 2015). The International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) is the global accounting standard recommended for entrepreneurial accounting across the globe. It divides accounting in the private sector into two broad categories: debit basis and credit basis of accounting.

Debit-based accounting reports all revenues that have been received during a period (Champoux, 2016). For credit basis of accounting (Flynn, *et. al.* 2016; Hoque, 2018; Stefanescu & Turlea, 2011), posited that credit-based accounting is the best accounting method for holding managements accountable and transparent especially due to rising global economic crisis. United States of America, Australia and New Zealand were among the pioneers in the development of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) (Christensen, 2020; Guthrie, 2016; Pollanen & Loiselle-Lapointe, 2012). Financial reports should have certain characteristics in order to achieve quality reporting standard. Both IASB and IFRS are in agreement that high quality is achieved by adhering to objectives and the qualitative characteristics of financial information (IASB, 2008; 2010; IFRS, 2014).

1.1.3 Determinants of financial reporting quality

According to Isidro and Raonic (2012), the entity's specific characteristics exhibit a stronger association with financial reporting quality. This argument was in line with other researchers who asserted that organizations have more control on specific characteristics than other factors that determines financial reporting quality (Huang, Rose-Green, & Lee, 2012; Soderstrom & Sun, 2017; Waweru & Riro, 2013).

1.1.4 Timeliness:

Timeliness means having information available to decision-makers in good time to enable them make timely decisions, (IASB, 2010). Generally, the older the information, the less useful it is. Yurisandi and Puspitasari (2015), found that timeliness of financial reports decreased after IFRS adoption, though not significant. This, they attributed to increased mandatory disclosure in IFRS, and as such companies may need longer time to prepare the financial reports. Timeliness is measured as the number of days it takes the auditor to sign after the reporting date.

Timely reporting in emerging markets is of particular importance since information in these markets is relatively scarce and takes a longer time lag (Errunza & Losq, 2018). Timely reporting enhances decision-making and reduces information asymmetry. Hence, research on the determinants of timely reporting could help regulators in emerging capital markets to formulate better policies and enhance financial reporting practices. For the short-term signal effects of timeliness, Givolvy and Palmon (2018); Leventis and Weetman (2014), suggested that the price reaction to the disclosure of early earnings announcements is significantly more pronounced than the reaction to late announcements suggesting a decrease in the information content as the reporting lag increases. High degree of market reaction towards earnings announcements is indicated by the high degree of cumulative abnormal returns around the announcements date, meaning that there is high information content of the earnings announcements: Hence, companies that releases their annual reports earlier have higher information content than those that release annual reports later (Givolvy & Palmon, 2018; Chambers & Penmann, 2017).

1.1.5 Internal control

According to AICPA (2015), internal control is a plan and other coordinated means and ways by an organization to keep safe its assets, check coventness and reliability of data to increase its effectiveness and to ensure the settled management politics. Chabugwen and Kwasira (2014), defined internal control as an executive process of board of directors, management and employees to achieve efficiency and effectiveness of operations, reliability of financial accountability and observing laws and regulations of the government. Gupta (2010), internal control is a financial and operation management of the enterprise aimed at achieving profit from its performance.

According to COSO (2013), internal control is defined by Environment, Risk assessment, Information, and communication, supervision, and these definitions are supported by (IAI, 2012), which states that financial statements are a structured representation of financial position of an

entity. Internal control is a framework of arrangements and systems that give protection to a unit's assets and other different assets usable by the association, precise and dependable financial reporting confirmation, principles or laws and controls, consistent advancement, and accomplishment of productive and successful tasks (Dzomira, 2014).

1.1.6 Adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS)

The development of IFRS has its origin in the accounting profession as a way to improve the transparency and accountability of managements by improving and standardizing financial reporting (Delloitte & Touches, 2013; Ijeoma, 2014). Over the years, countries have defined and set the standards of financial reporting in their individual territories. However, globalization has brought about ever-increasing collaboration, international trade and commerce among the countries hence, there is grave need for increased uniformity in the standards guiding the preparation of financial statements so that such statements would remain comprehensible and convey the same information to users across the world. The need for the development of unified accounting standards has been the primary objective of IFRS for public sector financial reporting (Heald, 2013). IFRS refers to the recommendations made by the IASB under the auspices of the IFAC (Delloitte & Touches, 2013; IASB, 2008). IFRS are norms that govern the recognition, measurement, presentation and disclosure requirements in relation to transactions and events in business purpose financial statements.

The IASB issues IFRSs dealing with financial reporting under the debit basis and the credit basis of accounting (Kanellos, *et. al*, 2013). The primary role of the IASB is to ensure that published financial statements are uniform in content and in format and communicate precisely what they purport to convey leading to better informed assessments of the resource allocation decisions made by shareholders, thereby increasing transparency and accountability (Stephen, *et. al*, 2012). According to the International Federation of Accountants, IFAC (2009), IFRS are high quality financial reporting standards applicable in the business sector reporting transactions that takes care of shareholders' interest in presentation and disclosure of financial transactions that enhances the accountability and management of resources.

IFRS was born out of the far-reaching effects of global financial crisis where many business managers' accountability and transparency in the reporting of assets and liabilities were put under question. Therefore, IFRS was adopted in order to help improve on the processes and to avoid future crises. Bergmann (2011), argued that the 2008 financial crisis was an eye opener from the

fact that financial reporting systems of many organizations were unable to anticipate the problem in good time which reduced the level of accountability in the private sector. Therefore, IFRS was considered the best solution because of its comprehensive reporting framework that regulates the recognition, measurement, presentation, and disclosure requirements in the financial statements (Ernst & Young, 2012).

1.1.7 Institutional theory

Institutional theory was formulated by John Meyer and Brian Rowan in 1977. The theory argues that formal organizational structures reflected not only technical demands and resource dependencies, but also shaped by institutional force (Palthe, 2014). The core idea is that organizational structures and practices are either reflections or responses to rules, beliefs and conventions built into the wider environment. Standardized items, administrations, procedures, approaches, and programs work as capable myths and numerous associations embrace them ritualistically but conformity to institutionalized rules often conflicts sharply with efficiency (Meyer & Rowan, 1977). Institutional theory has been used in the prior research to explain the adoption of IFRS in some countries (Adhikari & Mellembvik, 2010; Christiaens, Vanhee, Manes-Rossi, Aversano, & van Cauwenberge, 2015; Nagalinagm, Mangala, & Kumudinie, 2015; Stan & Sven, 2016). These studies assumed that pressure is exerted by external forces on the organizations to conform with a set of expectations to gain legitimacy so as to secure access to vital resources and long-term survival.

Omoregie and Eromosele (2020), examined some factors affecting financial reporting quality in the Nigeria private sector using one hundred and fifty (150) copies of likert-scale questionnaire comprising fifteen questions (with three questions representing financial reporting quality and three questions representing each of the four explanatory variables) which were administered to civil servants, members of civil society organizations, legal practitioners, academics, and professional accountants in office of the auditor general of the federation. The estimation of the responses of ninety-five (95) useable retrieved questionnaire done with the aid of ordinary least square regression techniques shows that internal control has a significant negative relationship with financial reporting quality; Public account committee effectiveness has a significant negative relationship with financial reporting quality; Stringent penalty for financial misconduct has an insignificant negative relationship with financial reporting quality; and Adoption of IFRS has a significant positive relationship with financial reporting quality in Nigeria private sector. The

authors recommended that private sector accounting set-up in Nigeria should include efficient and effective internal control mechanism, professional audit firms and incorporation of IFRS relevant requirements into the financial statements reporting framework.

Muraina and Dandago (2019), examined the effects of the implementation of the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) on Nigeria's financial reporting quality. The study employed a survey research design to determine the effects of the implementation of the IFRS on Nigeria's financial reporting quality. Partial Least Square 3 (Smart PLS 3) technique of analysis was applied to achieve the research objective. The study found that accountability positively and significantly affects the quality of financial reporting in Nigeria. Specifically, IFRS has improved the level of accountability, which in turn improved Nigeria's financial reporting quality.

Nirwana and Haliah (2018), tested the determinant factors of the quality of financial statements and performance of the management by adding contextual factors, such as personal factor, system/administrative factor and political factor, that may affect the quality of financial statement information and performance of the management. Personal factors were proxies as the competencies that affect the quality of financial statements and performance. Social administrative factor was proxies as the regulations and presentation of quality financial statements. The analysis unit in this study was conducted at the organizational level. The result showed that personal factors of competence affect financial statements' quality.

Olayinka, Okoye, Modebelu, and Olaoye (2016), examined the impact of IFRS adoption on the quality of financial reporting in the Nigerian private sector. 164 respondents selected from the account departments of business organizations in Lagos State were sampled for the study. The study used regression analysis method to investigate the impact of IFRS adoption on the quality of financial reporting in the private sector. The study adopted adjusted R^2 as a primary metric for measuring the model specification. The regression result shows that IFRS adoption has a significant positive impact on the quality of financial reporting in the Nigerian private sector. The study recommended that regulatory authorities should adopt adequate measures to ensure compliance by those saddled with the responsibility of preparing private sector financial statements. Also, measures should be taken to enhance the disclosure of relevant financial information that will help users take useful economic decisions.

The study maintained that this facilitates the reconciliation between budgeted and actual results as it would be necessary to align the budget preparation to full accrual as well as the enhancement of existing capacity, allowing reporting and comparison of budget against actual results would also allow for improvement in results- based budgeting.

This study is therefore set to fill the gap by examining the determinants of financial reporting quality in Nigerian public entities using secondary data from the annual report of agripreneurship companies in Nigeria from 2003 to 2024, with the following objectives; while the main objective of the study is to examine the determinants of financial reporting quality in the agripreneurship companies in Nigeria, the specific objectives are as follows;

1. To determine the effect of internal control disclosure on timeliness of annual reports of agripreneurship companies in Nigeria.
2. To explain the effect of management financial expertise on timeliness of annual reports of agripreneurship companies in Nigeria.
3. To ascertain the effect of agripreneurship's adoption of the IFRS in its business.

Accordingly the following research questions were formulated for the study;

1. What is the effect of internal control disclosure on timeliness of annual reports of agripreneurship companies in Nigeria?
2. How does management financial expertise affect timeliness of annual reports of agripreneurship companies in Nigeria?
3. To what extent does the adoption of IFRS affect timeliness of annual reports of agripreneurship companies in Nigeria? Also, the following null hypotheses were tested.

H0₁: Internal control disclosure has no significant effect on timeliness of annual reports of agripreneurship companies in Nigeria.

H0₂: Management of financial expertise has no significant effect on timeliness of annual reports of agripreneurship companies in Nigeria.

H0₃: Adoption of IFRS has no significant effect on timeliness of annual reports of agripreneurship companies in Nigeria.

The *ex-post facto* research design was adopted for this study since the study intended to determine the cause-effect relationship between the independent and dependent variables with a view to establishing a causal effect of the determinants of financial reporting quality of public entity in Nigeria. The study considered the agripreneurship companies in Nigeria as its object of population.

The reason for the selection was accessibility to the annual reports of the public entity for twenty one (21) years from 2003 to 2024. However, due to the nature of this study, the sample size twenty one (21) was the same as the population of the study twenty one (21).

Secondary data were used to derive useful information needed for the successful conduct of this research study. Secondary data collection is the gathering of information already researched and presented by other scholars or data obtained from other sources. The secondary data were acquired through related literatures, textbooks, management science journals, magazines, newspapers and others. Specifically, the study relied on the annual report of the agripreneurship companies in Nigeria during a 21-year period (2003 to 2024). On the other hand, entrepreneurial activities are critical in molding our lives and well-being. This is because entrepreneurship has suddenly become a policy tool in combating unemployment, rising poverty, economic inequality, and food insecurity (Yusoff, *et al.*, 2019; Arafat, *et al.*, 2020).

According to (Magagula & Tsvakirai, 2020), agripreneurship is considered a growth engine in many countries, potentially eliminating poverty while also increasing economic growth and development. Entrepreneurship fosters value creation in terms of opportunity and socio-economic well-being in the economy. It primarily aids in regulating economic activity by taking the following actions: 'developing new businesses, refocusing existing enterprises,' and reorienting national institutions' (Yusoff, *et al.*, 2019; Arafat, *et al.*, 2020; Magagula & Tsvakirai, 2020).

Agripreneurship is a relatively new concept that denotes an innovative way of generating wealth increment from the agriculture sector. Different terminologies emerged to describe the concept. Most scholars refer to it as agricultural entrepreneurship, farm entrepreneurship, agripreneurship, or agro-entrepreneurship (Yusoff, *et al.*, 2016; Pindado & Sánchez, 2017).

However, it is observed that these different terminologies could lead to confusion. Dias, *et al.*, (2019a) suggested a unified definition to avoid confusion. Given this, scholars attempted to devise

a comprehensive definition. Agripreneurship, for example, is defined by (Nagalakshmi & Sudhakar, 2013), as "usually sustainable, community oriented, directly-marketed agribusiness."

According to Bairwa, *et al.*, (2014), it is a combination of agriculture and entrepreneurship that eventually leads to agribusiness. Yusoff, *et al.*, (2016), stated that agripreneurship could be defined as creating a venture incorporating innovation elements in the agriculture sector. More recently, (Verma, *et al.*, 2018,) explained that agripreneurship is adopting new methods, procedures, and techniques in agriculture, or the allied areas of agriculture, for better output and economic earnings.

2. Theoretical Review

Accounting information system is considered to be one of the most important systems of any organization. Its objective is to provide necessary information to the managers at different levels. This information helps them in discharging their responsibilities in an effective and different manner in the areas of planning, resource control, performance evaluation and decision-making (Hosen, *et al.*, 2013).

From a logical assessment, a nations' economy consists largely of two principal sectors: agriculture and industry. Agriculture to a large extent is rural based and industry brain. According to Price water house Coopers (PwC, 2016), contributions of agriculture to Nigeria's real GDP in the fourth quarter of 2015 was 24.18%. This, it reported, was due to the introduction of mechanised farming and the agribusiness value chain, the government encouraged this development in agriculture as a precursor to poverty alleviation through agribusiness aided by investments from commercial farmers. With the fall in the price of crude oil in the international market in recent times, the government is emphasizing agricultural exports as an alternative foreign exchange earner. The

articulation and introduction of entrepreneurial principles into agriculture will be a strong driver of this programme and improvement on what has been achieved so far in the agricultural sector.

Agriculture today in Nigeria is facing challenges that are yet to be addressed such as inadequate infrastructure, difficulty in accessing credit and absence of training for smallholder farmers on opportunities that the enterprise offers, training experts to handle the accounting system to facilitate geometric production process in agriculture among other constraints in modern farming techniques. Mitigating these will assist in improving Nigeria's food security, develop agribusiness, grow the GDP and raise foreign exchange earnings (PwC, 2016). Other challenges are volatile insecurity level, kidnapping and banditry ravaging our country in general, and the rural farmers in particular all of which have given rise to soaring food prices that are technically beyond the reach of the common man, changes in climatic systems that have changed patterns of agricultural practices and adaptable crops, rapid urbanisation that has altered production and consumption patterns; the list is endless. These developments have ushered in changes in the food markets, created very slim opportunities and huge challenges for the farmers, especially the smallholders. For the agricultural sector to remain competitive in the global economy, new ideas must be developed and processes for value creation in a sustainable manner devised. (Uneze, 2013). Nigeria's Agricultural policy is targeting food security, import substitution to mitigate the massive food import and conserve foreign exchange, job creation and enhancing economic diversification and growth. These objectives can be achieved if we run agriculture as a business and encourage private-sector led engagements as the main objective driver. This commercialization orientation will involve the application of technologies such as through the accounting information systems, development of input supply chains, market linkages and financial services that engage the farmers.

These are critical to job creation, economic diversity, and sustainable economic growth (Ado, 2017). Therefore, it is of great importance to develop and present agriculture in the context of product development, value addition, and as a business that is knowledge driven. Hence, its unequivocal ties with efficient accounting information system at work. The addition of business knowledge to agriculture birthed agribusiness and, the incorporation of entrepreneurial principles into agribusiness have evolved agripreneurship. Hence, the concept of agripreneurship is the combination of agriculture and entrepreneurship.

Agripreneurship is an employment strategy that will ensure self-reliance and economic self-sufficiency. Agripreneurship is the profit oriented marriage of agriculture and entrepreneurship; it turns a farm into an agribusiness (Birwa, *et al*, 2014). Moreover, the study identified a host of factors influencing agripreneurship behavior. Personality traits, psychological, and contextual factors such as perceived government support and social networking were highlighted as essential determinants driving agripreneurship ventures. Most research revealed that agripreneurship orientation, skill, personality traits, perceived government, family and friends' support significantly impact business performance. Essentially, the review highlighted several challenges affecting agripreneurship development in Nigeria, such as lack of government support, discouragement from family and friends, poor infrastructure, imperfect market institution, lack of agripreneurial skills, and inadequate credit facilities for agripreneurship ventures.

This study employed analytical software of Stata version 14 and Microsoft excel for the analysis. The secondary data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation, and regression analysis. The descriptive statistic was used to evaluate the characteristics of the data: mean maximum, minimum, and standard deviation and also check for normality of the data. Correlation analysis was employed to evaluate the association between the variables and to check for multicollinearity. Regression analysis technique was employed to find the cause effect relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variables. However, this method of analysis

helps to establish the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable of interest and to identify the direction of the relationship. It reflects the level to which a set of variables is capable of predicting a specific outcome.

In this study, the model was specified to capture the determinants of financial reporting, hence the study adapted the model of Rahmatika (2016), which was modified for the purpose of establishing the relationship between the dependent variables and the linear combinations of several determining variables captured in the study. Specifically, the econometric form of the model was expressed as:

$$FRQT_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 INCO_{it} + \beta_2 EMED_{it} + \beta_3 IPSAS_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

Where:

FRQT	=	Financial Reporting Quality
INCO	=	Internal Control
EMED	=	Employee Education
IFRS	=	Adoption of IFRS
β_0	=	Constant
$\beta_1 - \beta_3$	=	Slope Coefficient
μ	=	Stochastic disturbance
i	=	Organisation
t	=	time-period

3. Data presentation, Analysis and Discussion

This study investigated the determinants of financial reporting quality of agripreneurship companies in Nigeria from 2003-2024. In this study, internal control disclosure, management financial expertise, and IPSAS adoption were the explanatory variables of this study while financial reporting quality was measured in terms of annual report timeliness. This section of the study presents the pre-regression analysis which included the descriptive statistics, test for normality data, as well as multicollinearity statistics. The regression analysis as well as the test for hypotheses of the study is also discussed in this section.

3.1 Data presentation

The data set for this study is presented in appendix A. However, in an attempt to achieve the objectives of this study, the study conducted a pool least square regression analysis then proceeded to check (diagnose) for inconsistencies with the basic assumptions of the pool OLS estimation

technique as provided by Woodridge (2012). Specifically, the study also performed some preliminary regression analysis that included descriptive statistics, correlation matrix and normality of data. However, the results are analysed as follows.

3.2 Descriptive statistics analysis

In this section, the study provided some basic information for both the explanatory and dependent variables of interest. Each variable was described based on the mean, standard deviation, maximum and minimum. Table 4.1 displays the descriptive statistics for the study.

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistic

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Frqt	21	73.105	33.589	21	127
Icds	21	.684	.478	0	1
Mfxp	21	3.632	2.033	1	7
Ifrs	21	.316	.478	0	1

Sources: Author's Computation, 2025

The results from the descriptive statistic presented in table 4.1 indicate that the mean of the dependent variable of financial reporting quality (FRQT) as measured in terms of timeliness of annual report was 73.11 with a standard deviation of 33.589. The result further indicate that, on average, during the period under study, it took the external auditor about 73 days to sign the audit report after the reporting date for agripreneurship companies in Nigeria. In the case of the independent variable, the results shows that internal control disclosure (ICDS) had a mean of 0.68 with a standard deviation of 0.478 indicating that during the period under study debt management office disclose 68% of internal control information. Furthermore, it was found that management financial expertise (MFXP) had a made of 3.632 with a standard deviation of 2.033 indicating that on average about 4 of the management had accounting qualification or related during the period under study. Finally, the mean of IFRS adoption was 0.316 and a standard deviation of 0.478.

The result indicates that on average, about 32% of the financial reports were prepared in line with IPSAS guidelines during the period under study.

3.3 Normality test

A plethora of normality tests can be found in the existing body of literature. The most frequently employed normality test procedures found in statistical software include the Shapiro-Wilk (SW) test, Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) test, Anderson-Darling (AD) test, and Lilliefors (LF) test. Certain tests within the scope of this study are subject to specific conditions or assumptions for their applicability. Additionally, it is worth noting that various tests assessing normality frequently yield

disparate outcomes. Specifically, certain tests may lead to the rejection of the null hypothesis of normality, while others may fail to reject it. The presence of contradictory results in research studies can be misleading and potentially confusing for practitioners in the field.

The present investigation utilized the Shapiro-Wilk test to assess the normality of the data.

The Shapiro-Wilk tests, initially developed by Shapiro and Wilk in 1965, were originally designed to be applicable to sample sizes that were smaller than 2000. The study conducted by Althouse *et al.* (2018), introduced a novel test that successfully identified deviations from normality caused by skewness, kurtosis, or both. The rationale behind employing the Shapiro-Wilk test to assess data normality is supported by the research conducted by Mendes and Pala (2013), because of its popularity, as well as Keskin (2016). These studies revealed that the Shapiro-Wilk test is the most effective method for evaluating normality. Particularly, when testing for normality, where the probabilities are greater than ($>$) 0.05, it indicates that the data are NORMAL. Conversely, where the probabilities are less than ($<$) 0.05, it indicates that the data are NOT NORMAL.

Table 4.2: Shapiro-Wilk Test for Data Normality

Variable	Obs	W	V	Z	Prob>z
frqt	21	0.958	0.967	-0.068	0.527
icds	21	0.932	1.550	0.881	0.189
mfxp	21	0.956	1.012	0.025	0.490
ifrs	21	0.931	1.584	0.924	0.178

Source: Author's, Computation, 2025

Table 4.2 shows that the dependent variable of financial reporting quality as measured in terms of timeliness of annual report has a z-statistics from the Shapiro-Wilk test as -0.068 with a pprobability of Z-statistic as 0.527. The result indicates that the dependent variable of financial reporting quality is normally distributed since the probability of the z-statistic as seen in table 4.2 is insignificant at 5% level. The same can be said of the independent variables of internal control disclosure with a z-statistics from the Shapiro-Wilk test as 0.881 with a Probability of Z-statistic as 0.189, management financial expertise with a z-statistics from the Shapiro-Wilk test as 0.025 with a Probability of Z-statistic as 0.490, and IPSAS adoption with a z-statistics from the Shapiro-Wilk test as 0.934 with a Probability of Z-statistics as 0.178 since their probabilities of the z-statistic as seen in table 4.2 are insignificant at 5% level. Hence, the study proceeds with parametric regression in line with the recommendations of Guajarati, (2014).

3.4 Data analyses

In order to achieve the objectives of the study, the pool ordinary least square (OLS) regression is conducted before proceeding to check for inconsistencies with the basic assumptions of the OLS regression. Succinctly, these diagnostics tests include test for multicollinearity as well as test for heteroscedasticity. However, the study first tests for the association between the independent variables and the dependent variables employed in the study using the Spearman Rank correlation.

3.5 Correlation analysis

In the field of statistics, it is well-established that the correlation coefficient, a measure of the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two variables, is bound by the values of +1 and -1. When the correlation coefficient approaches ± 1 , it indicates a high degree of association between the two variables, suggesting a strong linear relationship. As the magnitude of the correlation coefficient approaches zero, it indicates a diminishing strength in the association between the two variables. In the field of statistics, it is customary to assess the strength and direction of relationships between variables through correlation analysis. This analytical technique encompasses three commonly employed correlation measures: Pearson correlation coefficient, Kendall rank correlation coefficient, and Spearman correlation coefficient. The Pearson correlation coefficient is a commonly employed statistical measure utilized to assess the strength and direction of the linear association between variables.

The Kendall rank correlation is a statistical test employed to assess the degree of association between two variables, without making any assumptions about the underlying distribution of the data. This non-parametric method quantifies the strength of dependence between the variables under investigation. The Spearman rank correlation test is a statistical method that does not make any assumptions about the distribution of the data. It is particularly suitable for conducting correlation analyses when the variables under investigation are measured on a scale that is at least ordinal. In this study, the Spearman rank correlation was employed since the observations are less than 2000. The result obtain from the Spearman correlation is presented in table 4.3

Table 4.3: Correlation Analysis

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
(1) frqt	1.000			
(2) icds	0.496	1.000		
(3) mfxp	0.926	0.418	1.000	
(4) ifrs	0.806	0.218	0.816	1.000

Spearman rho = 0.816

Source: Author's Computation, 2025

In the case of the correlation between the independent and dependent variables under study, the result from table 4.3 shows that internal control disclosure (0.496) has a positive association with the dependent variable of financial reporting quality during the period under study. Furthermore, we find that management financial expertise (0.926) also has a positive association with the dependent variable of financial reporting quality during the period under study. Finally, we find that IFRS adoption (0.806) has a positive association with the dependent variable of financial reporting quality during the period under study. However, to test the hypotheses a regression results will be needed since correlation test does not capture cause-effect relationship.

3.6 Regression analyses

Specifically, to examine the cause-effect relationships between the dependent variables and independent variables as well as to test the formulated hypotheses, the study used the pool OLS regression, and the result is presented below:

Table 4.4: Regression result

Linear regression

Frqt	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Icds	12.165	5.118	3.71	.005	-3.007	27.337	**
Mfxp	12.722	3.312	3.84	.002	5.663	19.781	**
Ifrs	7.058	13.313	0.53	.604	-21.318	35.435	
Constant	16.352	8.292	1.97	.067	-1.322	34.026	
Mean dependent var		73.105	SD dependent var			33.589	
R-squared		0.879	Number of obs			19	
F-test		36.210	Prob > F			0.000	
Akaike crit. (AIC)		154.356	Bayesian crit. (BIC)			158.134	
VIF		3.55					
Hetttest		0.02	{0.8834}				

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$

Source: Author's Computation, 2025

The table above represents the results obtained from the regression estimation of the model. The result indicates that the pool OLS regression had an R-squared value of 0.879. This implies that the independent variables of the study could explain about 88% of the systematic change in the

dependent variable of financial reporting quality during the period under study. However, the unexplained part of financial reporting quality has been captured by the error term. The result of the F-statistics (32.210) of the pool OLS regression with the associated p-value of 0.0000 indicates that the pool OLS regression on the overall are statistically fit at 1% level of significance and can be employed for statistical inferences. However, to further validate the estimates of the pool OLS results, this study also tested multicollinearity and heteroscedasticity.

3.7 Test for multicollinearity

Multicollinearity can mainly be detected with the help of tolerance and its reciprocal, called variance inflation factor (VIF). The results obtained from the mean VIF reveal a value of 3.55 indicating that the mean VIF is within the benchmark of 10 and in line with the position of (Gujurati, 2014). This implies that the absence of multicollinearity and further shows that none of the independent variables should be dropped from the models respectively.

3.8 Test for heteroscedasticity

The test of the assumption of homoscedasticity of the pool OLS is conducted using the Breusch Pagan module in Stata 14. In particular, the assumption of homoscedasticity states that if the errors are heteroscedastic then it will be difficult to trust the standard errors of the least square estimates. Hence, the confidence intervals will be either too narrow or too wide. The result shows a chi2 value of 0.20 with a p-value of 0.8834. The result shows an insignificant p-values for the model indicating that the assumption of homoscedasticity of the pool OLS regression results have not been violated. Hence, the results of the OLS regression presented in table 4.4 can be relied upon to test the hypotheses of this study.

3.9 Test of hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Internal control disclosure has no significant effect on timeliness of annual reports of the agripreneurship companies in Nigeria.

The results obtained from the pool OLS regression model presented in table 4.4 revealed that internal control disclosure [coef. = 12.165 (0.005)] has a significant positive effect on timeliness of annual reports the agripreneurship companies in Nigeria during the period under study. The result implies that an increase in internal control disclosure will significantly increase the timeliness of annual reports of the agripreneurship companies in Nigeria during the period under study. Thus, the null hypothesis that internal control disclosure has no significant effect on timeliness of annual reports of the agripreneurship companies in Nigeria are rejected.

Hypothesis 2: Management of financial expertise has no significant effect on timeliness of annual reports of the agripreneurship companies in Nigeria.

The results obtained from the pool OLS regression model presented in table 4.4 revealed that management financial expertise [coef. = 12.722 (0.002)] has a significant positive effect on timeliness of annual reports of the agripreneurship companies in Nigeria during the period under study. The result implies that an increase in the number of directors with financial expertise will significantly increase the timeliness of annual reports of the agripreneurship firms in Nigeria during the period under study. Thus, the null hypothesis that management financial expertise has no significant effect on the timeliness of annual reports of the agripreneurship firms in Nigeria are rejected.

Hypothesis 3: Adoption of IFRS has significant effect on timeliness of annual reports of the agripreneurship firms in Nigeria.

The results obtained from the pool OLS regression model presented in table 4.4 revealed that Adoption of IFRS [coef. = 7.058 (0.604)] has a significant positive effect on timeliness of annual reports of the agripreneurship firms in Nigeria during the period under study. The result implies that the adoption of IFRS significantly increase the timeliness of annual reports of agripreneurship firms in Nigeria during the period under study. Thus, the null hypothesis that adoption of IFRS has significant effect on timeliness of annual reports of the agripreneurship firms are accepted.

3.10 Discussion of findings

In this study, it was found that internal control disclosure has a significant positive effect on timeliness of annual reports of agripreneurship firms in Nigeria during the period under study.

The result implies that an increase in internal control disclosure will significantly increase timeliness of annual reports of agripreneurship firms in Nigeria during the period under study.

Effective internal control over financial reporting gives sensible affirmation with respect to the unwavering quality of financial reporting and plan of financial explanations for external purposes.

This activity gives sensible confirmation, both to management and investors, about the financial status of the public entity.

Sovereign governments additionally distribute their financial statements, and these have far reaching-suggestions. The financial statements of sovereign governments affect their universal quality and are very significant in the present set of global business. Hence, there is consistency with the studies of Permatasari and Yulianto, (2020), who noted that poor internal control is viewed

as the essential motivation behind why extortion happens. Internal control and financial reporting have gotten expanded consideration particularly since the Tread Way Commission (1987), distinguished the tone set by senior management as the most critical factor adding to the honesty of financial reporting procedure (Alves, 2020; Putra, *et al.*, 2019; Dewi & Suryanawa, 2014).

Furthermore, the study found that management financial expertise has a significant positive effect on timeliness of annual reports of the agripreneurship firms in Nigeria during the period under study. The result implies that an increase in the number of directors with financial expertise will significantly increase timeliness of annual reports of the agripreneurship firms in Nigeria during the period under study. Although managers tend to possess superior technical knowledge, analytical skills, and the habit of precise communication, they often know little about the competitive environment and customers' tastes (Wennberg, *et. al.*, 2011). The decision to join corporate ranks can be driven by reasons that have little to do with the merits of the new job, such as the desire to mimic the decisions of more successful colleagues (Stuart & Ding 2016).

Finally, it was found that adoption of IFRS has a significant positive effect on timeliness of annual reports of the agripreneurship firms in Nigeria during the period under study. The result implies that the adoption of IFRS significantly increase timeliness of annual reports of the agripreneurship firms in Nigeria during the period under study. IFAC encouraged public sector entities to adopt an accrual basis of accounting for their general-purpose financial statement so as to ensure uniformity and comparability of financial reporting across countries (Udeh & Sopekan, 2015).

4. Summary of findings, conclusion and recommendations

4.1 Summary of findings: This study investigated the determinants of financial reporting quality of the agripreneurship firms in Nigeria from 2003-2024. In this study, internal control disclosure, management financial expertise, and IFRS adoption were the explanatory variables of the study while financial reporting quality was measured in terms of annual report timeliness. To achieve the objectives of the study, the pool least square regression estimation was conducted before proceeding to check for inconsistencies with the basic assumptions of the OLS regression. Succinctly, these diagnostics tests included test for multicollinearity as well as test for heteroscedasticity. The study also performed preliminary pre-regression analysis such as descriptive statistics, correlation matrix and normality test. The results of the empirical findings with respect to each specific objective of the study are as follows.

1. Internal control disclosure [coef. = 12.165 (0.005)] has a significant positive effect on timeliness of annual reports of the agripreneurship firms in Nigeria during the period under study.
2. Management financial expertise [coef. = 12.722 (0.002)] has a significant positive effect on timeliness of annual reports of the agripreneurship firms Nigeria during the period under study.
3. Adoption of IFRS [coef. = 7.058 (0.604)] has a significant positive effect on timeliness of annual reports of the agripreneurship firms in Nigeria during the period under study.

4.2. Conclusion

In conclusion, financial reporting quality is crucial in maintaining the efficiency of financial markets because market participants, such as investors, lenders, and regulators, rely on financial reporting information to make decisions. Financial reporting thus, requires the arrangement of accounting related information by the administration to address the issues of different users such as government, regulators, suppliers, customers, management, and investors (both potential and existing investors). Accurate and qualified financial reports are considered an effective tool for conducting financial analysis, feasibility analysis and interpretation. Financial reporting quality can be defined as the precision with which financial reporting conveys information about the firm's operations, its expected cash flows, to inform equity investors. Providing high quality financial reporting information is important because it will positively influence capital providers and other stakeholders in making investment, credit, and similar resource allocation decisions. According to the International Federation of Accountants, IFAC (2009), IFRSs are high quality financial reporting standards applicable in the business sector reporting transactions that takes care of shareholders' interest in presentation and disclosure of financial transactions that enhances the accountability and management of resources.

Hence, this study investigated the determinants of financial reporting quality of the agripreneurship firms in Nigeria from 2003 to 2024.

5. Recommendations

1. This study has sufficiently established different positions on the determinants of financial reporting quality. Based on the findings of this study, it was carefully recommended that government of Nigeria should ensure that the internal control system is periodically monitored and

evaluated. The actual assessment can be executed by the organization's management in order to promote financial reporting quality among public entities in Nigeria.

2. Based on the findings of the study, the agripreneurship firms in Nigeria should ensure that more of those Directors with financial expertise are employed and retained so as to increase the quality of financial reporting in the Nigeria. Staff development, annual promotion exercises to the ranks of Directors coupled with financial expertise training should be prioritized by the agripreneurship firms in Nigeria.

3. Last but not the least, the agripreneurship firms in Nigeria should prioritize the adoption of IFRS especially if such policies are meant to increase the quality of financial reporting of the agripreneurship firms in Nigeria.

Definition of operational terms and Acronyms

1. Agripreneurship: Agripreneurship is typically an employment strategy that ensures self-reliance and economic self-sufficiency. It is the nexus between agriculture and entrepreneurship which turns a farm into agribusiness anchoring on profit motives.

2. IFRS: This is an international financial organization which exist to direct all organisations, particularly those operating with profit motives behind their mandate to apply a common financial transaction which can be measurable in financial terms from all parts of the world where the shareholders chose to operate from without fear of being cheated.

3. IASB: This is yet another international financial authority or institution which exists to ensure that all the countries' financial standards are set in accordance with the one international accounting standard board all with a view to ensuring fair and equity in interpretation of their transactions in monetary terms.

4. IFAC: This is the international federation of accountants' body, the institution which serves the public and private sector interests by strengthening the global accountancy profession, developing and promoting high-quality international standards like auditing, ethics in both private and public sector organisations.

Contribution to knowledge: This research has contributed to existing volume of knowledge in no small measure by researching on the impact of financial reporting quality on agripreneurship in Nigeria. Agripreneurship is a relatively new area in research. Moreover, it is largely a privately operated line of business enterprise in the time being. This is because the government of Nigeria has been concentrating herself with the provision of the not-for-profit service organizations to Nigerians as it were. So, the knowledge of quality financial reporting gained through this research will enhance the private agripreneurship to a greater extent than before now, and by extension provide a boost to the Nigerian economy.

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